

Pest Control and Management

DISEASES

Effect of synthetic pyrethroids on tungro (RTV) incidence and vector control

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Two formulations of synthetic pyrethroid cypermethrin (Ripcord and Cymbush), two other synthetic pyrethroids, decamethrin and FMC

54800, and carboiuran were evaluated against RTV and its vector.

Cypermethrin, decamethrin, and FMC 54800 were sprayed every 10 d beginning 15 d after transplanting (DT) to 45 DT. Carbofuran was broadcast at 15-d intervals. Test cultivars were TN I (susceptible) and Ratna (tolerant). Plot size was 3 × 3 m in a randomized block design with 3 replications for each cultivar. RTV epidemic conditions were created by

planting three infected tillers of Jaya in the middle of each plot. Disease incidence, grain yield, and leafhopper population were measured.

Cypermethrin and decamethrin were equally effective in reducing RTV incidence and leafhopper population in both varieties (see table). Carbofuran and fenvalerate were also effective in Ratna. FMC 54800 was not as effective as the other synthetic pyrethroids. □

Effect of synthetic pyrethroids on RTV and its vector on TN1 and Ratna cultivars. Cuttack, India.^a

Insecticide	Concentration (%)	Disease incidence (%)		Grain yield (t/ha)		Leafhoppers/20 hills at 33 DT			
		TN1	Ratna	TN1	Ratna	TN1		Ratna	
						Adult	Nymph	Adult	Nymph
Cypermethrin (Cymbush)	0.01	7 c	1 a	3.9 ab	4.5 ab	0 a	0 a	0 a	0 a
	0.05	5 b	1 a	4.1 a	4.5 ab	0 a	0 a	0 a	0 a
Cypermethrin (Ripcord)	0.01	6 bc	1 a	3.9 ab	4.4 ab	0 a	0 a	0 a	0 a
	0.05	3 a	1 a	4.0 a	4.5 a	0 a	0 a	0 a	0 a
Decamethrin	0.005	11 d	1 a	3.6 bc	4.3 abc	0 a	1 a	0 a	0 a
	0.01	5 b	1 a	4.0 a	4.6 ab	0 a	0 a	0 a	0 a
FMC 54800	0.01	100	39 e	1.0 f	2.9 d	6 c	27 d	4 b	10 c
	0.05	79	18 d	1.6 e	3.1 abcd	3 b	3b	1 bc	1 a
Fenvalerate	0.01	17 e	14 c	3.0 d	3.3 bcd	0 a	0 a	1 bc	0 a
	0.05	10 d	5 b	3.5 c	3.8 abcd	0 a	0 a	0 a	0 a
Carbofuran	2 kg	26 f	4 b	2.9 d	4.3 abc	3b	11 c	2 c	3 b
Control	–	100	51 f	0.3 g	2.5 d	13 d	40 e	7 e	37 d

^a In a column, values followed by the same letter do not differ significantly by DMRT (P = 0.05).

Association of *Humicola* sp. with stem rot (SR) complex in Haryana

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Plants infected with a disease similar to SR have been observed at Kaul since 1980. Patches of wilted rice plants (Jaya variety) were observed at postflowering during Oct 1984. Culms were water-soaked with reddish brown lesions without distinct margins. Cavities of the lower 3-4 internodes

revealed off-white to dirty black hyphal masses concentrated near the nodes. At maturity, the sheaths of affected plants blackened up to 15-20 cm above soil level. Plants broke off at the crown and could be easily pulled, leaving most of the roots in the soil. Grains were partially filled and discolored.

Microscopic examination of mycelial mats revealed septate hyphae hyaline when young and brown when older. The fungus was easily isolated on PDA. Colonies were white at first, turning grey to black with production

of numerous black conidia. The causal agent, identified as *Humicola* sp., proved pathogenic only when inserted inside the culm.

In a survey during 1984 kharif, wet crown rot was noticed at other sites. The pathogen occurred alone and in association with three sclerotial fungi: *Sclerotium oryzae*, *S. oryzae* var. *irregulare*, and *S. hydrophilum*. Affected hills could be classed into three categories (see table). *Humicola* sp. was associated more with category 1, but only where the stool was pulled out after breaking at the crown.

In varietal screening trials against SR fungi, *Humicola* sp. was recorded on 54 entries. Nineteen varieties were most susceptible: Tadukan, M. sung song, Jhona 349, HKR207, HAU53-4618-2-1, HAU118-358, HAU120-326, HAU98-8, C-1321-9, C-1158-7, HAU10-194-1, HAU6-11-1-1-1-1, HAUS-145-1, HKR111, Pusa 33, IR29692-65-2-3, IR25861-35-3-3, IR25890-82-5-3, and IR13538-48-2-3-2. □

Association of SR fungi with wet culm crown rot at RRS, Kaul, India.

Category	Description	SR association (% tillers)			
		<i>S. oryzae</i>	<i>S. oryzae</i> var. <i>irregularare</i>	<i>S. hydrophilum</i>	<i>Humicola</i> sp.
1	Whole stool easily pulled out, breaking at crown, roots left inside soil	30	25	100	100
2	Partial stool pulled out	10	–	50	50
3	Stool pulled out with difficulty, roots intact	20	20	100	–

Acquired resistance of rice leaves to *Rhizoctonia solani*

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Sheath blight (ShB) incited by *Rhizoctonia solani* is a major fungal disease of rice. Acquisition of ShB resistance in excised rice leaves has been worked out through prior interaction with an avirulent *R. solani* isolate.

Several isolates from rice and other field crops were screened on TKM9 and Ponni for relative virulence. Avirulence on rice of isolate R7 from potato was further confirmed on CO 43 and IR50.

Leaves excised from 60-d-old field-grown rice plants were floated on 5 ppm kinetin to delay senescence and inoculated with a rice grain culture of R7. The leaves were challenged with sclerotia of virulent isolate R1 / R5 at 12 h. Disease spread was scored every 24 h from 48 h after challenge inoculation to 120 h.

In leaves preinoculated with R7, sclerotia of the virulent isolate did not spread until 72 h and formed only a few lesions, for 90% protection (see figure).

The generally slow-growing avirulent isolate R7 showed neither antibiosis nor parasitism and was overgrown by R5 in dual culture. Histopathological studies revealed sparse growth of R7 at the site of

Effect of incompatible interaction on ShB severity. DSI = av no. of lesions/leaf × av lesion length (cm).

inoculation, with inability to produce infection cushions on rice leaves. Direct penetration of the mycelium through either stomata or cuticle was not observed.

The fact that 60-65% protection against ShB could be obtained even when leaves were challenge-inoculated where R7 had not spread (2-3 cm

away) rules out direct antagonism between the 2 RS isolates and any competition for entry, colonization, and leaf exudates. Activation of host defense mechanisms might be responsible for acquired resistance. Preinoculation of rice leaves (prior-interaction) with R7 successfully induced protection. □